

A Study on the Impact of Life Happiness on Job Performance

Hasan Tezcan UYSAL^a, Murat AK^b, Hasan GÜDÜK^c

^a Şeyh Edebalı Üniversitesi, Bilecik, Türkiye - h.tezcanuysal@hotmail.com - ORCID No: 0000-0002-8962-7824

^b Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey Üniversitesi, Karaman, Türkiye - muratak1578@hotmail.com - ORCID No: 0000-0003-2292-1444

^c Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey Üniversitesi, Karaman, Türkiye - hasanguduk@hotmail.com - ORCID No: 0000-0003-0744-3894

ÖZ

Bu çalışmada, okul yöneticilerinin yaşam mutluluğunun iş performansına etkisi olup olmadığı ve yaşam mutluluğunun demografik faktörlere göre anlamlı bir farklılık gösterip göstermediği araştırılmaktadır. Bu doğrultuda resmi kurumlarda görev yapan okul yöneticilerine yönelik bir uygulama gerçekleştirilmiştir. Anket tekniğinin kullanıldığı araştırmadan elde edilen veri setleri, SPSS paket programı ile değerlendirilmiştir. Bu program kapsamında gerçekleştirilen analizler sonucunda; yaşam mutluluğu ve iş performansı arasında pozitif yönlü bir ilişki tespit edilmiş, yaşam mutluluğundaki 1 birimlik artışın yöneticilerin iş performansı üzerinde 1.237 birimlik bir artışa neden olduğu saptanmıştır. Bununla birlikte yaşam mutluluğunun eğitim düzeyine, yaşa göre, medeni duruma göre, gelire göre, görev yapılan okul türüne göre ve görev süresine göre anlamlı bir farklılık gösterdiği belirlenmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İş Performansı, Okul Yönetimi, Yaşam Mutluluğu, Yönetici Davranışı.

ABSTRACT

This study investigates whether the life happiness of school administrators has an impact on job performance and whether life happiness shows a significant difference according to demographic factors. In this direction, an application has been carried out for school administrators working in official institutions. The data sets obtained from the research where the survey technique has been used have been evaluated with SPSS package program. As a result of the analyses carried out within the scope of this program; a positive relationship has been found between life happiness and job performance, and it has been determined that a 1-unit increase in life happiness caused a 1,237-unit increase in managers' job performance. However, it has been determined that life happiness showed a significant difference according to education level, age, marital status, income, school type, and tenure.

Keywords: Job Performance, School Management, Life Happiness, Manager Behavior.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Educational practices are activated with strong and effective management studies and at the same time, information flow is provided. Essentially, school; When considered with a holistic approach, management philosophy should be in cooperation with planning. For all actors, the curriculum must have an important mission and be central. Basically, the main point is; It is possible to reveal possible management problems during the educational activity in the classroom. In this context, it is desired to emphasize that a successful school administration, increasing student productivity, and high standard education and training activities depend on appropriate management projections and programs. Considering that school administrators undertake the leadership mission, the management of the educational curriculum together with learning; The curriculum also includes coordination and control functions. In the context of the leadership of school principals, the dimension of managing learning and school program undertakes the coordination and control of the curriculum and teaching. When evaluated in the context of a country, school programs constitute the fleshed-out form of education policies. In general, while preparing school programs, it should be aimed to raise individuals with critical thinking by considering the personal qualities of the students, and differences should be considered as richness. In order for the school administrator to be successful, he must understand the roles of the employees well and exhibit appropriate behaviours. The ability of schools to achieve their predetermined objectives depends on the efficiency of the school principal, who is responsible for all of the work and operations in the school. Studies on effective school show that school management has a critical importance in the formation of impactful school (Balci, 2002). Since educational activities are considered extremely important today, many studies are carried out to increase the success of education. Since the performance of school principals, who are the managers of educational institutions, will increase the quality of education, it is also important to determine the variables affecting the performance of school principals. Therefore, with this study, the possible impact of life happiness of school administrators on job performance will be examined.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Job Performance

The concept of job performance is a difficult to understand concept that does not have a generally agreed definition among the authors. Stefan (2011) defines performance as the result of actions over a period of time. Campbell (1990) defines performance as behavior or actions related to the goals of the organization. On the other hand, Viswesvaran and the Ones (2000) introduces a combination of the above definitions by defining performance as measurable actions, behaviours and outcomes in which employees participated, which are related and contribute to the goals of the organization (Erbaş, 2019).

The re-evaluation of the concept of performance has been and continues to be a priority of economic research, finding indicators that better reflect the intricacies of the functioning of economic assets. The concept of performance is a reference both in theoretical approaches and in practice due to the fact that the field of economic performance includes various terms, most importantly competitiveness, efficiency, profitability, business growth. In a simple etymological analysis of this term, we can find that it is a term with wide use in various fields (sports, mechanics, economy), and this term turns into a very meaningful term over time on the basis of the covered field activity (Uyargil, 2013: 23-25). Regardless of the domain, the term performance leads us to success, competition, action, effort, and progress. If we want to provide a universal definition of performance, we must perceive it as a system of sometimes contradictory, sometimes even contradictory, complementary parameters, drawing on the results obtained by the analysed subject and the process of obtaining these results (Tutum, 2014: 41-43). Assessing an organization's employee as part of a performance

appraisal is a difficult process that requires patience. Because today, the job performance of employees is affected by many factors. The organizational system that aims to plan, evaluate and improve the performance of employees, which considers the concept of performance evaluation as a dynamic process, is today called the performance management system (Baştemur, 2006:34-37).

Job performance is defined as “the total expected value for the organization of discrete parts of behavior that an individual performs over a standard period of time. This definition is a slightly revised version of the definition of performance presented in a previous publication in connection with the theory of individual differences in task and contextual performance” (Motowidlo et al., 1997:71). According to Murphy (1989:227), job performance can be defined as “the sequence of behaviours related to the goals of the organization or organizational unit in which a person works”. Therefore, an individual's job performance plays a vital role in the growth of an organization. This is because it highly influences the performance of the overall firm and also functions as a key variable in business and organizational psychology. However, individual job performance is not constant and can fluctuate over time. Research has shown that by changing the time spent in a particular job, an individual's performance changes. At the same time, individual performance changes as a result of learning, and high performance is always the result of a better understanding of a particular job rather than putting more effort into it. Furthermore, fluctuating individual job performance may result from patterns of change within the individual or changes in the psycho-physiological state of the individual (Zacher, 2009).

On the other performance is considered one of the most important structures in human resources research. Motowidlo et al. (1997) state that an individual's behavior may differ from work performance over time in the workplace. This is because behavior is what people do, and job performance is the predictable and expected organizational value of what people do. Therefore, not all actions are classified as performance, and not all actions can solve organizational problems. Only actions that are relevant and scalable and can be measured are considered organizational value, goals, and success performance. Due to the importance of fiction in human resources work, job performance can be a key indicator of the effectiveness of an organization's human resource management system. When individuals are well educated and equipped, the ability to compete at a national and even international level improves the performance of employees. Thus, this helps to achieve economic success and increase the reputation of the organization (Ferguson & Reio, 2010).

Empirical evidence has shown that performance rewards are a powerful management tool that can be used to build a high-performing organization as their contributions and efforts motivate individuals to perform better as they are recognized, valued, and appreciated. Research has shown that monetary rewards and incentives play an important role in attracting and retaining the best performing employees. Trahant and Yearout (2006) suggested that employers should ensure that meaningful financial rewards are set aside for employee outstanding performance. This is because employees do not take the reward and incentive systems and principles seriously if financial rewards are not given.

Today, performance-based income is a common type of payment system in many organizations. According to established human resource management models, performance-based payment is a unique payment system that functions as one of the key roles in human resources strategies together with the performance evaluation system (Fombrun et al., 1984). It is also known as one of the financial reward systems that differs from traditional payment systems and is often carried out collectively (Shelley, 1999). Helm et al. (2007) note that although many organizations implement pay-for-performance programs, very few organizations define and specify the goals of their performance management systems, align goals with corporate strategic plans, and even evaluate the conditions or process of success.

2.2. Life Happiness

Happiness and meaning in life are indirectly related to both anxiety and depressive symptoms through their positive association with perceived stress (Hills & Argyle, 2002). Happiness has been defined as a permanent, complete and justified satisfaction from life as a whole. According to Kraut (1979), happiness involves the belief that a person is getting the important things they want and some pleasant impacts that normally go along with that belief. According to Hills and Argyle (2002) “happiness is a multidimensional structure that includes both emotional and cognitive elements”. Three main components of happiness have been identified. These are frequent positive emotions or joy, a high average level of satisfaction over a period of time, and the absence of negative emotions such as depression and anxiety.

The study of happiness theories is important because it describes how people think about happiness, which can be associated with certain behaviours toward self and others that aim to increase happiness. The goal theory claims that happiness is gained when a situation, goal, or need is fulfilled. Activity theories emphasize that happiness can be achieved through social interaction, leisure, or other specific activities. According to the goal theory introduced by Wilson in 1960, meeting needs leads to happiness, and unmet needs lead to unhappiness (Diener & Ryan, 2009). The foundations of well-being are seen as the last point to be reached in theory. This means that the theory is based on the assumption that subjective well-being occurs when a person succeeds in his effort to achieve the desired goals. Ryan and Deci's (2000) Self-Determination Theory has suggested that the individual has some innate needs that he or she seeks to fulfill in order to achieve well-being.

According to the Psychological Well-Being Theory; the term hedonic well-being is normally used to express subjective feelings of happiness. It consists of two components, the emotional component (high positive impact and low negative impact) and the cognitive component (life satisfaction). It is suggested that when both positive emotion and life satisfaction are high, the individual experiences Happiness. The lesser-known term Eudaimonic well-being is used to refer to the purposeful aspect of psychological well-being. Psychologist Carol Ryff has developed a very clear model that divides Eudaimonic well-being into the six basic types of psychological well-being. Theories about psychological well-being often focus on understanding the structure or dynamics of psychological well-being. The separation of psychological well-being into hedonic and Eudaimonic components and Carol Ryff's model are widely accepted theories regarding the structure of psychological well-being (Ryff & Keyes, 1995: 722-724).

When it comes to the dynamics of psychological well-being, it is important to recognize that to some extent it is relatively stable and will be influenced by both previous experiences and the underlying personality. Stressful experiences can predispose people to later mood and anxiety disorders. On the other hand, exposure to extremely traumatic events can help build resilience and actually maintain psychological well-being. For example, children exposed to moderately stressful events seem to be better able to cope with subsequent stressors (Ryff & Keyes, 1995: 722-724). While basic psychological well-being is fairly stable, everyday events and experiences also make an impact. For example, even the most resilient person may eventually become very low or depressed if their daily experience is consistently uncomfortable. There is strong evidence to suggest that prolonged exposure to work-related stressors will have a negative impact on psychological well-being. Therefore, as mentioned, short-term periods of distress can be helpful in building endurance (Şirin & Ulaş, 2015).

The theory of multiple inconsistencies has been developed by Michalos in 1985. This theory suggests that the subjective well-being of individuals depends on comparisons made based on a multitude of criteria. Individuals compare past circumstances with themselves, other people's standards, goals, and ideal levels of fulfillment to determine their subjective levels of well-being. By comparing existing conditions with ideal

standards, the individual decides his level of well-being; to find the current situation higher than ideal standards means that inconsistency results in increased satisfaction, and vice versa, inconsistency results in decreased satisfaction (Diener, 1984).

Dynamic equilibrium theory has been proposed by Headey and Wearing (1989). In this theory, it is claimed that the level of subjective well-being is kept constant without significant life events taking place, and that if an experience leads to a change in subjective well-being, it returns to the previous level after a while. In the model, personality is the main determinant of individuals' basic level of subjective well-being (Headey, 2008). In other words, even if the subjective well-being levels of individuals change after positive and negative events, they return to the level of balance determined by their personality. It is also stated that there is a relationship between being good (life satisfaction, positive impacts) and bad.

In the literature, many terms are happily used interchangeably, including life satisfaction, flow, peak experiences, well-being, and quality of life. Reflecting a psychological or subjective well-being, happiness refers to a state of mind associated with the success or satisfaction of desires or needs. Saturation is similar to happiness, but it does not refer to a state of mind. That is, success can be accompanied by a positive state of mind, and the absence of success can be accompanied by negative emotions; however, mental state is not a defining characteristic of satisfaction. Therefore, a person may or may not be satisfied with health, housing, finances, etc.; happiness is a more global structure (Özer & Karabulut, 2003).

Similar to life satisfaction, quality of life, another concept in the literature, although broader than happiness, is another concept that is sometimes used interchangeably with happiness. Meeberg (1993: 33-35) identifies four critical attributes of quality of life. These are the feeling of satisfaction with one's life in general, the mental capacity to evaluate one's own life in a satisfying or otherwise way, an acceptable state of physical, mental, social and emotional health.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. The Population and Sample of the Research

The population of the research consists of school administrators working in official institutions. The sample of the study consists of school administrators working in official institutions in Karaman. According to the calculation for the sample volume, it has been determined that it would be sufficient to obtain data from 219 school administrators. In this context, data has been collected from 242 people on a voluntary basis. The statistically reached sample number represents the population for a margin of error of 5%. However, in general, the number of samples between 200 and 300 is considered sufficient in screening type researches in social sciences (Gürbüz & Şahin, 2014).

3.2. The Data Collection Method and Data Analysis of the Research

The data obtained from the scales used within the scope of the research have been entered into the computer environment and analysed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) program. The data found to be incomplete and erroneous have been not included in the analysis. In addition, empty items in the data set have been identified before the analysis has been started and the average values have been assigned for the lost data. After this process, the total scores and subscores of the scales used have been calculated. Descriptive statistical methods (number, percentage, frequency, average) have been used to evaluate the data. It has been assumed that the sample should show a normal distribution in order to apply parametric test methods to the evaluation of the data (Kalaycı, 2010). The skewness and flatness values of the data have been examined in order to evaluate the normality of the distributions for the obtained scores.

Skewness and kurtosis values have been examined to determine whether the variables used in the study had a normal distribution. Kalaycı (2010) states that if the skewness and kurtosis measure takes values in the range of -3 to +3, it will show normal distribution. In the study, the flatness and distortion values of the end-of-the-end scale are given in the table below. With the establishment of normality, the use of parametric methods has been preferred in the analysis of the data. Simple linear regression analysis has been performed to examine whether life happiness has an impact on job performance. In addition, differential analyses have been performed to determine whether life happiness differed according to gender, age, education level, marital status, income, branch and school type worked.

Table 1: Distortion and Flatness Values of Life Happiness and Job Performance

Variable	Skewness	Kurtosis
Life Happiness	0,441	-0,689
Job performance	-0,433	-1,130

3.3. The Research Model

Relational screening model has been used in the study. In this context, life happiness and work performance variables are discussed. Job performance has been used as the dependent variable and life happiness has been used as the independent variable. The hypotheses put forward within the scope of the research are as follows:

H1: Life happiness has a positive impact on job performance.

H2: Life happiness varies according to demographic characteristics, school type and tenure.

H2a: Life happiness varies according to gender.

H2b: Life happiness varies according to age.

H2c: Life happiness varies according to the level of education.

H2d: Life happiness varies according to marital status.

H2e: Life happiness varies according to income.

H2f: Life happiness varies according to the branch.

H2g: Life happiness varies according to the school type worked.

H2h: Life happiness varies according to the duration of the task.

4. RESULTS

Table 1 contains descriptive statistics. As can be seen in this table, 32% of the managers participating in the research are women and 68% are men. 69.4% of the sample are married and 30.6% are single. When age distributions are examined, it is observed that 73.5% of the sample consists of managers between the ages of 31-50. 80.8% of the managers have monthly income (including salary and additional courses) in the range of TRY 19001-23000 and it is observed that 91.8% of them have been working for more than 5 years. In terms of educational status, it is understood that the majority of 58.4% are undergraduate graduates. The proportion of managers in the culture course branch has a majority in the sample with 44.7%. However, when examined in terms of school type, it is observed that there is a balanced distribution among the subgroups in terms of sample.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	70	32%
	Male	149	68%
Marital Status	Single	67	30.6 %
	Married	152	69.4 %
Age	20-30	26	11.9 %
	31-40	82	37.4 %
	41-50	79	36.1 %
	51 and older	32	14.6 %
Income	TRY 17000-19000	9	4.1 %
	TRY 19001-21000	89	40.6 %
	TRY 21001-23000	88	40.2 %
	TRY 23001-25000	24	11%
	TRY 25000 and above	9	4.1 %
Tenure	1-5 Years	18	8.2 %
	6-11 Years	59	26.9 %
	12-17 Years	57	26%
	18-23 Years	42	19.2 %
	24 years and more	43	19.6 %
Education Level	Associate	11	5%
	Bachelor's Degree	128	58.4 %
	Post-Graduate	73	33.3 %
	Doctorate	7	3.2 %
Line of Business	Vocational Course	51	23.3 %
	Culture Course	98	44.7 %
	Class Teacher	41	18.7 %
	Kindergarten Teacher	6	2.7 %
	Other	23	10.5 %
School Type	Basic Training	60	27.4 %
	Secondary	60	27.4 %
	Religious Teaching	25	11.4 %
	Vocational and Technical Education	62	28.3 %
	Other	12	5.5 %

The internal consistency values obtained as a result of the reliability analysis performed for the scales used in the research are expressed in Table 3. Since Cronbach's Alpha values are greater than 0.6, it has been determined that there is high internal consistency (Akgül & Çevik, 2003).

Table 3: Alpha Values for Life Happiness and Job Performance

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Life Happiness	0,909
Job performance	0,956

The results of simple linear regression analysis performed to test the hypotheses put forward in the research are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Regression Analysis Results

Model		Non-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	r2	F	Model Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta					
1	(Stable)	-0,448	0,276		-1,621	0,106	0,516	231,686	0,000
	Life Happiness	1,237	0,081	0,719	15,221	0,000			

As can be seen in the table above, in the established regression equation, the impact of life happiness on the level of work performance has been found to be statistically significant. Life happiness has been found to explain 51.6% of the variance in the job performance score [F(1.217=231.686); p<0.001]. When the standardized beta coefficient has been examined, it has been found that life happiness had a positive and significant predictive impact on work performance ($\beta= 0.72$; p<0.001). Thus, hypothesis H₁ has been accepted.

Table 5: T Test for Life Happiness and Gender

		Average of Variances		T test for Equality of Averages						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Average Difference	Standard Error difference	Difference in 95% Confidence Interval	
									Lowest	Highest
Life Happiness	Acceptance of equal variances	0.18	0,672	-1,395	217	0,164	-0.11192	0.08022	-0.27002	0.04618
	Rejection of equal variances			-1,352	125,171	0,179	-0.11192	0.08277	-0.27573	0.05189

As seen in Table 5, it has been found that life happiness did not show a statistically significant difference according to gender. Therefore, hypothesis H_{2a} has been rejected. Table 6 shows the gender-based mean and standard deviation values of the variables.

Table 6: Gender Based Average and Standard Deviation Values of Variables

	Gender	N	Avg.	Standard Deviation
Life Happiness	Female	70	3.2773	0.58632
	Male	149	3.3893	0.53763

As seen in Table 7, a statistically significant difference in life happiness has been found in favour of married people in both groups according to marital status. Thus, hypothesis H_{2d} has been accepted.

Table 7: T Test for Life Happiness and Marital Status

		Average of Variances		T test for Equality of Averages						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Average Difference	Standard Error difference	Difference in 95% Confidence Interval	
									Lowest	Highest
Life Happiness	Acceptance of equal variances	13,876	0,000	-4,569	217	0,000	-0.3558	0.0778	-0.5093	-0.2023
	Rejection of equal variances			-5,019	159.17	0,000	-0.3558	0.0708	-0.4958	-0.2157

Table 8 shows the mean and standard deviation values of the variables based on marital status.

Table 8: Marital Status Based Average and Standard Deviation Values of Variables

	Marital Status	N	Avg.	Standard Deviation
Life Happiness	Single	67	3.1065	0.44248
	Married	152	3.4623	0.56549

As can be seen in Table 9, as a result of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether life happiness showed a significant difference according to age, the difference between the arithmetic averages of the groups has been found to be significant. Thus, hypothesis H_{2b} has been accepted.

Table 9: One-Way Analysis of Variance for Life Happiness and Age (ANOVA) and Standard Deviation Values

		Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom:	Avg. of Squares	F	p
Life Happiness	Between Groups	8,841	3	2,947	10,877	0,000
	Intra-Group	58,254	215	0,271		
	Total	67,095	218			
		N	Avg.	Standard Deviation		
Life Happiness	20-30	26	2.9828	0.34788		
	31-40	82	3.2254	0.51299		
	41-50	79	3.5037	0.57288		
	51 and older	32	3.6121	0.51787		
	Total	219	3.3535	0.55478		

Complementary Post-Hoc analyses have been initiated in order to examine which groups had the significant difference determined by ANOVA analysis. In order to decide which Post-Hoc multiple comparison technique to use after ANOVA analysis, as can be seen in Table 10, the homogeneity of the variances has been first checked through the Levene Test and it has been seen that the variances have been not homogeneous. After this process, the Games Howell multiple comparison technique, which is used in cases where the variances are not homogeneous, has been preferred.

Table 10: Results of the Variance Homogeneity Test on Life Happiness Levels

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Life Happiness	3,986	3	215	0,009

As can be seen in Table 11, as a result of the Games Howell test, which has been conducted to determine between which age groups the perception of life happiness of the participants constituting the sample group showed a significant difference, it has been determined that the difference in question has been in favour of the 41-50 age group among all other groups except the age group of 51 and above.

Table 11: Games Howell Test Results for Life Happiness and Age Scores

Dependent Variable	(I) AGE	(J) AGE	Average Difference (I-J)	Standard Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Life Happiness Games-Howell	20-30	31-40	-.24264	0.08868	0,039	-0.4767	-0.0085
		41-50	-.52095	0.09386	0,000	-0.7679	-0,274
		51 and older	-.62931	0.11417	0,000	-0.9319	-0.3267
	31-40	20-30	.24264	0.08868	0,039	0.0085	0.4767
		41-50	-.27831	0.08581	0,008	-0.5012	-0.0555
		51 and older	-.38667	0.10766	0,004	-0.6717	-0.1016
	41-50	20-30	.52095	0.09386	0,000	0,274	0.7679
		31-40	.27831	0.08581	0,008	0.0555	0.5012
		51 and older	-0.10836	0.11196	0,768	-0.4038	0.1871
	20-30	.62931	0.11417	0,000	0.3267	0.9319	

	51 and older	31-40	.38667	0.10766	0,004	0.1016	0.6717
		41-50	0.10836	0.11196	0,768	-0.1871	0.4038

As can be seen in Table 12, a significant difference has been found between the arithmetic means of the groups as a result of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether life happiness showed a significant difference according to income. Thus, hypothesis H_{2e} has been accepted.

Table 12: ANOVA and Standard Deviation Values for Life Happiness and Income

		Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom:	Avg. of Squares	F	p
Life Happiness	Between Groups	6,595	4	1,649	5,832	0,000
	Intra-Group	60,501	214	0,283		
	Total	67,095	218			
		N	Avg.		Standard Deviation	
Life Happiness	TRY 17000-19000	9	2.8008		0.13105	
	TRY 19001-21000	89	3.2383		0.51506	
	TRY 21001-23000	88	3.5051		0.57029	
	TRY 23001-25000	24	3.4885		0.54633	
	TRY 25000 and above	9	3.2031		0.48197	

Complementary Post-Hoc analyses have been initiated in order to examine which groups had the significant difference determined by ANOVA analysis. After ANOVA analysis, the homogeneity of the variances has been checked through the Levene Test in Table 13 in order to decide which Post-Hoc multiple comparison technique to use, and it has been seen that the variances have been not homogeneous. After this process, the Games Howell multiple comparison technique, which is used in cases where the variances are not homogeneous, has been preferred

Table 13: Results of the Variance Homogeneity Test on Life Happiness Levels

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Life Happiness	4,096	4	214	0,003

As can be seen in Table 14, as a result of the Games-Howell test, which has been conducted to determine between which income groups the perception of life happiness of the participants constituting the sample group showed a significant difference, the difference in question is between the manager group with a monthly income of TRY 17000-19000 and the manager group with a monthly income of TRY 25000 or more between all other groups except the manager group with a monthly income of TRY 17000-19000 group. It has been determined that the difference between the manager group with monthly income between TRY 21001-23000 and the manager group with monthly income between TRY 19001-21000 has been realized in favour of the managers with monthly income between TRY 21001-23000.

Table 14: Games Howell Test Results for Life Happiness and Income Level

Dependent Variable	(I) INCOME	(J) INCOME	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Life Happiness	TRY 17000-19000	TRY 19001-21000	-0.43751	0.06992	0,000	-0.6366	-0.2384
		TRY 21001-23000	-0.70433	0.07486	0,000	-0.9160	-0.4927
		TRY 23001-25000	-0.68774	0.11977	0,000	-1.0362	-0.3393
		TRY 25000 and above	-0.4023	0.16649	0,194	-0.9598	0.1552
	TRY 19001-21000	TRY 17000-19000	0.43751	0.06992	0,000	0.2384	0.6366
		TRY 21001-23000	-0.26681	0.08171	0,011	-0.4921	-0.0416

	TRY 21001-23000	TRY 23001-25000	-0.25023	0.12417	0,280	-0.6073	0.1069
		TRY 25000 and above	0.03521	0.16968	1,000	-0.5238	0.5943
		TRY 17000-19000	0.70433	0.07486	0,000	0.4927	0,916
		TRY 19001-21000	0.26681	0.08171	0,011	0.0416	0.4921
		TRY 23001-25000	0.01659	0.12701	1,000	-0.3471	0.3803
		TRY 25000 and above	0.30203	0.17177	0,443	-0.2588	0.8628
	TRY 23001-25000	TRY 17000-19000	0.68774	0.11977	0,000	0.3393	1.0362
		TRY 19001-21000	0.25023	0.12417	0,280	-0.1069	0.6073
		TRY 21001-23000	-0.01659	0.12701	1,000	-0.3803	0.3471
		TRY 25000 and above	0.28544	0.19557	0,601	-0.3126	0.8835
	TRY 25000 and above	TRY 17000-19000	0.40230	0.16649	0,194	-0.1552	0.9598
		TRY 19001-21000	-0.03521	0.16968	1,000	-0.5943	0.5238
		TRY 21001-23000	-0.30203	0.17177	0,443	-0.8628	0.2588
		TRY 23001-25000	-0.28544	0.19557	0,601	-0.8835	0.3126

As can be seen in Table 15, as a result of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether the life happiness of the individuals showed a significant difference according to tenure, the difference between the arithmetic averages of the groups has been found to be significant. Thus, hypothesis H_{2h} has been accepted.

Table 15: ANOVA and Standard Deviation Values for Life Happiness and Tenure

		Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom:	Avg. of Squares	F	p
Life Happiness	Between Groups	9,977	4	2,494	9,345	0,000
	Intra-Group	57,118	214	0,267		
	Total	67,095	218			
		N		Avg.	Standard Deviation	
Life Happiness	1-5 Years	18		3.0747	0.36479	
	6-11 Years	59		3.0883	0.45143	
	12-17 Years	57		3.3829	0.56220	
	18-23 Years	42		3.6174	0.62510	
	24 years and more	43		3.5373	0.47096	

Complementary Post-Hoc analyses have been initiated in order to examine which groups had the significant difference determined by ANOVA analysis. In order to decide which Post-Hoc multiple comparison technique to use after ANOVA analysis, as can be seen in Table 16, the homogeneity of the variances has been first checked through the Levene Test and it has been seen that the variances have been not homogeneous. After this process, the Games Howell multiple comparison technique, which is used in cases where the variances are not homogeneous, has been preferred.

Table 16: Homogeneity Test Results of Variance on Life Happiness and Tenure

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Life Happiness	4,120	4	214	0,003

As can be seen in Table 17, as a result of the Games-Howell test, which has been conducted to determine between which age groups the perception of life happiness of the participants constituting the sample group showed a significant difference, it has been determined that the difference in life happiness occurred against the 1-5 years group between the 1-5 years and the 1-5 years group between the 18-23 years group and the 24 years and over group. It has been found to be in favour of the 6-11 group in all other groups except the 6-11 years group and the 1-5 years group.

Table 17: Games Howell Test Results for Life Happiness and Tenure

Dependent Variable	(I) Tenure	(J) Tenure	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Games-Howell Life Happiness	1-5 Years	6-11 Years	-0.01354	0.10415	1,000	-0.3133	0.2862
		12-17 Years	-0.30823	0.11374	0,068	-0.6316	0.0151
		18-23 Years	-0.54269	0.12921	0,001	-0.9077	-0.1776
		24 years and more	-0.46258	0.11203	0,002	-0.7822	-0.1429
	6-11 Years	1-5 Years	0.01354	0.10415	1,000	-0.2862	0.3133
		12-17 Years	-0.29469	0.09486	0,020	-0.5579	-0.0315
		18-23 Years	-0.52915	0.11295	0,000	-0.8454	-0.2129
		24 years and more	-0.44904	0.09280	0,000	-0.7075	-0.1906
	12-17 Years	1-5 Years	0.30823	0.11374	0,068	-0.0151	0.6316
		6-11 Years	0.29469	0.09486	0,020	0.0315	0.5579
		18-23 Years	-0.23447	0.12186	0,313	-0.5743	0.1054
		24 years and more	-0.15435	0.10346	0,570	-0.4419	0.1332
	18-23 Years	1-5 Years	0.54269	0.12921	0,001	0.1776	0.9077
		6-11 Years	0.52915	0.11295	0,000	0.2129	0.8454
		12-17 Years	0.23447	0.12186	0,313	-0.1054	0.5743
		24 years and more	0.08012	0.12026	0,963	-0.2559	0.4161
24 years and more	1-5 Years	0.46258	0.11203	0,002	0.1429	0.7822	
	6-11 Years	0.44904	0.09280	0,000	0.1906	0.7075	
	12-17 Years	0.15435	0.10346	0,570	-0.1332	0.4419	
	18-23 Years	-0.08012	0.12026	0,963	-0.4161	0.2559	

As can be seen in Table 18, as a result of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether the life happiness of the individuals showed a significant difference according to the level of education, the difference between the arithmetic averages of the groups has been found to be significant in both variables. Thus, hypothesis H_{2c} has been accepted.

Table 18: ANOVA and Standard Deviation Values for Life Happiness and Education Level

		Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom:	Avg. of Squares	F	p
Life Happiness	Between Groups	2.74	3	0,913	3,051	0,030
	Intra-Group	64,356	215	0,299		
	Total	67,095	218			
			N	Avg.	Standard Deviation	
Life Happiness	Associate		11	3	0.31679	
	Bachelor's Degree		128	3.3766	0.54896	
	Post-Graduate		73	3.4043	0.58681	
	Doctorate		7	2.9557	0.21874	

Complementary Post-Hoc analyses have been initiated in order to examine which groups had the significant difference determined by ANOVA analysis. In order to decide which Post-Hoc multiple comparison technique to use after ANOVA analysis, as can be seen in Table 19, the homogeneity of the variances has been first checked through the Levene Test and it has been seen that the variances have been not homogeneous. After this process, the Games Howell multiple comparison technique, which is used in cases where the variances are not homogeneous, has been preferred.

Table 19: Variance Homogeneity Test Results on Life Happiness and Education Level

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Life Happiness	6,117	3	215	0,001

As can be seen in Table 20, as a result of the Games-Howell test, which has been conducted to determine between which education level groups the perception of life happiness of the participants constituting the sample group showed a significant difference, it has been determined that the difference in life happiness has been realized between the associate education group and the undergraduate education group and the graduate education group against the associate degree education group. It has been determined that it has been realized between the doctoral education group and the undergraduate education group and the master's education group against the doctoral education group.

Table 20: Games Howell Test Results for Life Happiness and Education Level

Dependent Variable	(I) ED	(J) ED	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Games-Howell	Associate	Bachelor's Degree	-0.37662	0.10713	0,014	-0.6837	-0.0696
		Post-Graduate	-0.40435	0.11764	0,012	-0.7308	-0.0779
		Doctorate	0.04433	0.12633	0,985	-0.3176	0.4062
	Undergraduate	Associate	0.37662	0.10713	0,014	0.0696	0.6837
		Post-Graduate	-0.02773	0.08409	0,988	-0.2463	0.1909
		Doctorate	0.42095	0.09586	0,005	0.1315	0.7104
	Post-Graduate	Associate	0.40435	0.11764	0,012	0.0779	0.7308
		Bachelor's Degree	0.02773	0.08409	0,988	-0.1909	0.2463
		Doctorate	0.44868	0.10748	0,003	0.1422	0.7552
	Doctorate	Associate	-0.04433	0.12633	0,985	-0.4062	0.3176
		Bachelor's Degree	-0.42095	0.09586	0,005	-0.7104	-0.1315
		Post-Graduate	-0.44868	0.10748	0,003	-0.7552	-0.1422
		Bachelor's Degree	-0.95379	0.17611	0,001	-1.4945	-0.4131
		Post-Graduate	-1.16614	0.18812	0,000	-1.7208	-0.6115

As can be seen in Table 21, as a result of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether the life happiness of the individuals showed a significant difference according to the branch, the difference between the arithmetic averages of the groups has been not found to be significant in both variables. Therefore, hypothesis H_{2f} has been rejected.

Table 21: ANOVA and Standard Deviation Values for Life Happiness and Branch

		Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom:	Avg. of Squares	F	p
Life Happiness	Between Groups	2,011	4	0,503	1,653	0,162
	Intra-Group	65,084	214	0,304		
	Total	67,095	218			
			N	Avg.	Standard Deviation	
Life Happiness	Vocational Course		51	3.4192	0.53324	
	Culture Course		98	3.3054	0.58597	
	Class Teacher		41	3.2616	0.47249	
	Kindergarten Teacher		6	3.3276	0.52284	
	Other		23	3.5832	0.57465	

As can be seen in Table 22, as a result of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether the life happiness of the individuals showed a significant difference according to the school type, the difference between the arithmetic averages of the groups has been found to be significant in both variables. Thus, hypothesis H_{2g} has been accepted.

Table 22: ANOVA and Standard Deviation Values for Life Happiness and School Type

		Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom:	Avg. of Squares	F	p
Life Happiness	Between Groups	4.3	4	1,075	3,663	0,007
	Intra-Group	62,796	214	0,293		
	Total	67,095	218			
			N	Avg.	Standard Deviation	
Life Happiness	Basic Training		60	3.4598	0.49311	
	Secondary		60	3.3046	0.62212	
	Religious Teaching		25	3.0055	0.38728	
	Vocational and Technical Education		62	3.4388	0.5598	
	Other		12	3.3506	0.51333	

Complementary Post-Hoc analyses have been initiated in order to examine which groups had the significant difference determined by ANOVA analysis. In order to decide which Post-Hoc multiple comparison technique to use after ANOVA analysis, the homogeneity of the variances has been checked through the Levene Test, as can be seen in Table 23, and it has been seen that the variances are not homogeneous. After this process, the Games Howell multiple comparison technique, which is used in cases where the variances are not homogeneous, has been preferred.

Table 23: Results of the Homogeneity Test of Variance of the Level of Life Happiness in Relation to the school type

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Life Happiness	3,989	4	214	0,004

As can be seen in Table 24, as a result of the Games-Howell test conducted to determine between which school type groups the perception of life happiness of the participants constituting the sample group showed a significant difference, the difference in question has been made between the basic education school type group and the religious education school group in favour of the basic education school type group, It has been determined that vocational and technical education has been realized in favour of the vocational and technical education school type group between the vocational and technical education school type group and the religious teacher school type group.

Table 24: Life Happiness and Games for School Type Howell Test Results

Dependent Variable	(I) School Type	(J) School Type	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Games-Howell	Basic Training	Secondary	0.15517	0.10249	0,556	-0.1290	0.4393
		Religious Teaching	0.45425	0.10026	0,000	0.1718	0.7367
		Vocational and Technical Education	0.02095	0.09543	0,999	-0.2434	0.2853
		Other	0.10920	0.16128	0,959	-0.3874	0.6058
	Secondary	Basic Training	-0.15517	0.10249	0,556	-0.4393	0.1290
		Religious Teaching	0.29908	0.11158	0,067	-0.0133	0.6115
		Vocational and Technical Education	-0.13422	0.10726	0,721	-0.4314	0.1629
		Other	-0.04598	0.16855	0,999	-0.5553	0.4633
		Basic Training	-0.45425	0.10026	0,000	-0.7367	-0.1718

Religious Teaching	Secondary	-0.29908	0.11158	0,067	-0.6115	0.0133
	Vocational and Technical Education	-0.43330	0.10514	0,001	-0.7285	-0.1381
	Other	-0.34506	0.16721	0,279	-0.8530	0.1629
Vocational and Technical Education	Basic Training	-0.02095	0.09543	0,999	-0.2853	0.2434
	Secondary	0.13422	0.10726	0,721	-0.1629	0.4314
	Religious Teaching	0.43330	0.10514	0,001	0.1381	0.7285
Other	Other	0.08825	0.16436	0,982	-0.4135	0.5900
	Basic Training	-0.10920	0.16128	0,959	-0.6058	0.3874
	Secondary	0.04598	0.16855	0,999	-0.4633	0.5553
	Religious Teaching	0.34506	0.16721	0,279	-0.1629	0.8530
	Vocational and Technical Education	-0.08825	0.16436	0,982	-0.5900	0.4135

The results of the hypothesis tests carried out according to the findings revealed as a result of the analyses carried out with the data obtained for the hypotheses put forward within the scope of the research are expressed in Table 25. According to this table; H₁, H_{2b}, H_{2c}, H_{2d}, H_{2e}, H_{2g} and H_{2h} have been accepted, while H_{2a} and H_{2f} have been rejected.

Table 25: Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis	Definition	Conclusion
H1	Life happiness has a positive impact on job performance.	Accepted
H2a	Life happiness varies according to gender.	Rejected
H2b	Life happiness varies according to age.	Accepted
H2c	Life happiness varies according to the level of education.	Accepted
H2d	Life happiness varies according to marital status.	Accepted
H2e	Life happiness varies according to income.	Accepted
H2f	Life happiness varies according to branch.	Rejected
H2g	Life happiness varies according to the school type in which the task worked.	Accepted
H2h	Life happiness varies according to tenure	Accepted

5. CONCLUSION

As a result of the research conducted for school administrators; it has been observed that life happiness has a positive and high-level impact on job performance. However, it has been determined that life happiness varies according to education level, age, marital status, monthly income, school type, and tenure. It has been not found that life happiness did not show a statistically significant difference according to gender and branch. In life happiness, it has been observed that married individuals exhibit more life happiness than single individuals. It has been determined that the average of married individuals is high. When evaluated according to age, it has been determined that managers in the 31-40 age range showed more life happiness than managers in the 41-50 age range. When examined in terms of education level, it has been found that the happiness of life of undergraduate and graduate school administrators has been higher than the school administrators who graduated from associate and doctorate degrees. When life happiness is evaluated according to income level, it is observed that the life happiness of those who have a monthly income between TRY 17000-19000 from income groups is lower than that of managers with other income levels. When life happiness is evaluated according to tenure, it is found that the experience time is lower in less school administrators than in more administrators. When life happiness is evaluated according to the school type; It has been found that the life happiness of the administrators in the basic education and vocational and technical education groups has been higher than the administrators in the religious education group.

Removing school management from the scope of a secondary duty, staffing school administrators rather than carrying out them by assigning them in the form of 4 + 4, can positively affect the life happiness of school administrators. In addition, it is thought that drowning school administrators with legislation and narrowing

the areas of initiative adversely affect the happiness of life of administrators. When school administrators use their right of appointment, the appointment of school administrators as teachers by taking over the school administration adversely affects the happiness of life of school administrators. In addition, assigning examination / investigation duties to school administrators prevents school administrators from performing their primary duties and negatively affects life happiness.

The fact that the employees participating in this study are only school administrators limits the generalizability of the study. Therefore, applying the study to teachers in future studies may be useful in order to generalize the study. In addition, the fact that this study has been carried out only in a certain region and province limits the generalization to be made on school administrators. In future studies, comparative practices in different provinces may be useful for generalization on school administrators.

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